

EFFECT OF FIRE PARAMETERS ON STRUCTURAL BEHAVIOUR OF A RESTRAINED STEEL BEAM

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ABSTRACT

Fires have become a common threat in terms of both public and structural safety. The increased concern for structural fire safety led to understanding the structural response of different members exposed to fire. This begins with fire modelling where a fire scenario is simulated as fire curves of time temperature variation and the response of structure for these fire curves is further analysed. The interpretation of fire scenarios as fire curves is formulated based on factors such as the opening factor, which is the measure of the openings in a compartment; the thermal inertia of the compartment surroundings; and the fire load density, the amount of combustible materials available per unit floor area of a compartment. The variation of any of these factors affects the fire curve and thus the response of a structure. This paper deals with a study of the effect of variation in opening Factor, fuel load density and thermal inertia on the structural response of a Beam. It mainly focuses on the variation in deflections and axial forces. It was observed that the thermal inertia has the least effect on the structural response of the beam, even though the percentage variation in its value is much higher (269.94%) the residual forces and deflections varied only by 0.4% and 2.13% respectively where the same are found to be higher for a comparatively lesser variation in the magnitudes of other factors.

Keywords: Opening Factor, Thermal Inertia, Fire Load Density, Insulation, Fire Resistance Rating

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1. INTRODUCTION

Fire is a universal hazard. The occurrence of fire is more often a local phenomenon and is much more frequent. Thus, while other hazards are more likely to hit specific areas that are prone to these events, fire has no geographical restrictions. It is a threat to the built environment across the world.

Fires are potentially destructive. It can damage the infrastructure causing a threat to the structural safety of buildings. To analyse the structure exposed to fire, understanding the temperatures of gases in the surroundings in which a structure is exposed becomes essential. This is known as fire modelling. A fire scenario is modelled as Fire curves with temperature on the vertical axis and duration on the horizontal axis, this depicts the progression of gas temperatures with time.

Fire development in a compartment initially starts as local burning and gradually turns into a fully developed fire in the presence of adequate fuel and ventilation. This transition is smooth and called a flashover. Once fuel or oxygen gets depleted, the rate of burning decreases indicating decay or cooling phase. Hence, fire in a compartment is a function of fire load density, opening factor and thermal inertia of boundary. These parameters influence the maximum temperature, growth rate and duration of the compartment fire.

During the initial ignition, burning objects release radiant heat energy. The adjacent combustible material heats up and catches fire. This additional fuel continuously burns and a large amount of thermal energy is released leading to a rise in compartment temperature. The type and amount of combustible material present in a compartment influences the fire spread and the overall temperatures. The burning of fuel also increases the volume of hot gases, these gases get collected near the ceiling of the compartment. This creates pressure and hot air tries to push down the cool air beneath and escape from the openings. But the amount of cool air present underneath the hot gases being low, the cool air from outside enters the compartment giving no chance for hot air to get escaped. This inward flow of air provides adequate oxygen content for further combustion. This indicates the influence of the opening factor on compartment fire.

Fire growth is a complex process; it also depends on the interaction of fire with compartment boundaries. The thermal inertia of a compartment boundary is the sensitivity of that material to the temperature variation. It defines how slowly or fast the body temperature approaches the gas temperature. It depends on the density, thermal conductivity and specific heat capacity of the material a compartment boundary is made of. This property influences the fire spread in a compartment.

Therefore, variations in any of these parameters would influence the fire growth in a compartment which in turn influences the structural behaviour.

The opening factor depends on the compartment geometry and the thermal inertia depends on the properties of boundary enclosure which can be worked out easily for a given compartment. Whereas, obtaining the value of fire load density is not an easy task, due to the uncertainties involved in estimating its value. The fire load density which largely depends on the type of occupancy evaluated from the codes and standards might not completely interpret the real fire scenario. Because the value recommended by the codes and standards is a deterministic value (80% fractile) which would be same for the entire occupancy type irrespective of the fact that the amount of fuel available and the size would largely vary between the compartments within an occupancy type.

This variation in the fire load densities is shown in [1]. The author summarised a great quantity of fire load surveys conducted for office buildings revealing a huge variation in the fire load densities depending on the use and the area and developed a probabilistic approach for evaluating the fire load densities. There are also many other advancements towards the performance based studies to estimate the fire load densities [2] and their effect on the fire temperatures, the effect of openings [19, 22] and the different boundary materials [16, 17, 18, 21] are also studied.

But the majority of the studies in the existing literature represented the effect of these basic parameters (amount of fuel available, the geometry, openings, thermal inertia) on the fire growth in a compartment but the corresponding effect on the structural behaviour has not yet studied greatly. Hence, the current study involves evaluating the effect of opening factor, fire load density, and the thermal inertia on the structural behaviour of a beam element exposed to fire with one of these parameters varying each time and with a main focus on the deflection and axial forces.

2. PROBLEM DEFINITION

In order to achieve the objectives of the present study, renowned finite element software, ABAQUS, is used for analysis. A steel beam with partial fixity (75% of rotational restraint) of 9.14 m length and cross-section of W21x50 is considered for the analysis these dimensions are taken from [15]. The beam was subjected to a uniformly distributed load of 11.844 kN/m, which has both live and dead load components.

3. FIRE MODEL

The first step in the analysis of structures under fire is to obtain the design fire. The fire temperatures are calculated using the parametric time-temperature relations specified in Eurocode 1 [3]. This equation produces a time-temperature relationship for any combination of fire load, opening factor, and boundary materials.

To study the effect of these three parameters three separate cases are considered

- a) In order to study the effect of opening factor three values $0.04 \text{ m}^{1/2}$ for Design Fire 1, $0.06 \text{ m}^{1/2}$ for Design Fire 2 and $0.08 \text{ m}^{1/2}$ Design Fire 3 are considered. The thermal inertia of $840 \text{ J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$ and a fuel load density of 420 MJ/m^2 are maintained constant for all three cases. The fire curves thus obtained are represented in [Figure 1]
- b) The values of 609 MJ/m^2 , 546 MJ/m^2 , 483 MJ/m^2 , 420 MJ/m^2 , 357 MJ/m^2 , 294 MJ/m^2 and 231 MJ/m^2 are used for studying the effect of fire load density. These values had a variation in the multiples of 15% above and below the fire load considered in the previous case (420 MJ/m^2). The opening factor and thermal inertia of $0.04 \text{ m}^{1/2}$ and $840 \text{ J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$ respectively are used and they are maintained constant throughout. The corresponding results of fire modelling are shown in [Figure 1].
- c) The thermal inertia of $432.5 \text{ J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$, $720 \text{ J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$, $840 \text{ J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$, $1600 \text{ J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$ are used for the analysis considering different wall linings to study the effect of thermal inertia. The opening factor of $0.04 \text{ m}^{1/2}$ and a fuel load density of 420 MJ/m^2 are maintained constant throughout. Corresponding results are shown in [Figure 3].

All these fire parameter values are obtained from different existing literature [14, 15, 20].

Figure 1 Gas temperature with time for different opening factors

Figure 2 Gas temperature with time for different fire load densities

4. THERMAL ANALYSIS

On exposure to these temperatures the beam temperatures also rise which vary across the depth and also with the time. In order to obtain the variation of nodal temperatures with respect to time heat transfer analysis is performed in the cross section of the beam. The beam is provided with spray-applied fire resistive material (SFRM) type fire protection material. The properties of SFRM are obtained from [14] SFRM with a density of 300 kg/m^3 , a conductivity of 0.12 W/(mK) , and a specific heat capacity of $1,200 \text{ J/(kgK)}$ are used in the analysis which would greatly affect the nodal temperatures. It is designed to have a thickness of 10 mm in order to achieve a fire resistant rating of 2-h by considering the limiting deformation as a failure criteria. The deformation criteria as per the BS 476 standard [10] is used. As per this standard the failure is assumed to occur when the maximum displacement in the member exceeded $L/20 \text{ (mm)}$. Based on this failure criterion a smaller thickness could have been used to satisfy the required fire resistance rating.

Figure 3 Gas temperature with time for boundaries of different thermal inertia

However, as per the recommendations of AISC [5] a minimum thickness of 3/8 inch is required. The fire temperatures obtained in the fire modelling are given as an input in thermal analysis and these temperatures are applied to the fire exposed surfaces of the beam through surface film conditions and radiative interaction conditions in ABAQUS. The convection heat transfer coefficient ‘h’ is taken as 25 W/m²K under standard fire exposure and 35 W/m²K under natural fire exposure. The unexposed surfaces in the beam are subjected to ambient temperature conditions throughout the analysis. In the current analysis it is assumed to be three-sided exposure [Figure 4]. The cross-section of the fire exposed surface including the fire insulation is discretized using the 4-noded quadrilateral DC2D4 element. A tie constraint is applied at the steel-insulation interface which ensures that the nodal temperatures in the insulation and the steel section are the same at the interface. The insulation is assumed intact during the entire duration of the fire exposure.

Thermal properties of the steel (thermal conductivity [W/(mK)] and specific heat [J/(kgK)]) are considered to be temperature dependent [Figure 5] and [Figure 6], Stefan-Boltzmann constant was $5.67 \times 10^{-8} \text{ W/ m}^2 \text{ K}^4$. As output the nodal temperature is saved at 5 temperature points (for I-section) in order to be used as an input data for the structural analysis. The variation of nodal temperatures across the depth at these 5 points are shown for opening factor = 0.04 m^{1/2}, fire load density = 420 MJ/m² and the thermal inertia = 840 J/m²s^{1/2}K in [Figure 7].

Figure 4 Cross section of protected steel beam exposed to fire

Figure 5 Variation of conductivity of steel with temperature

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Figure 6 Variation of Specific Heat of steel with temperature

Other combinations also follow the same trend but, to show the comparison between them the temperature variations at TP1 (being the highest) are plotted [Figure 8, Figure 9, Figure 10].

Figure 7 Nodal temperatures with time for a protected steel beam at various temperature points

Figure 8 Nodal temperatures with time for different opening factors at TP1

Figure 9 Nodal temperatures with time for different thermal inertia at TP1

Figure 10 Nodal temperature with time for different fire load densities at TP1

5. STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

The structural model is dependent on the nodal temperatures in the beam as well as the mechanical properties of the steel beam and the magnitude of the load applied, which includes both dead and live load components. The initial elastic properties of the steel at ambient are as follows: density 7850 kg/m^3 , Poisson's ratio 0.3, expansion coefficient $1.2 \times 10^{-5} / ^\circ\text{C}$. Additionally, the Young's modulus and yield strength are taken as temperature dependent and their reduction factors are in accordance with Standard EN 1993-1-2:2004.

The nonlinear structural analysis is undertaken on 1D beam with the purpose of modelling the performance of beam under fire conditions. In order to deal with the geometric nonlinearity, namely, with the large displacements the nonlinear geometric parameter (NLGEOM=ON) was set.

The mid span deflection and the axial force at the ends of the beam are obtained for above mentioned three cases having different values of fire influencing parameters.

6. RESULTS

Opening factor

The results obtained from fire modelling [Figure 1] demonstrates that the gas temperatures reach their maximum levels more rapidly for higher opening factors, indicating faster burning rates due to increased oxygen supply, promoting faster combustion and subsequent cooling.

However, this trend is reversed in case of nodal temperatures of the beam due to the presence of insulation material. [Figure 8] indicates that for higher values of opening factor, by the time nodal temperatures reach their peak, the fire has already subsided, and gas temperatures have reverted to ambient levels. Hence, nodal temperatures are observed to be maximum for the compartment with lower opening factor.

• **Effect on Deflection**

[Figure 11] shows that initially in the heating phase, all the curves align together and part away after attaining maximum deflection. When the opening factor is varied from 0.08 m^{1/2} to 0.04 m^{1/2} the maximum deflection got increased by 80% (from 0.05912 m to 0.10649 m) and permanent deflections got increased by 37.84% (from 0.0444 m to 0.0612 m).

Figure 11 Variation of deflections with temperature for different opening factors

• **Effect on Axial Force**

For different values of opening factors, no significant change in the variation of axial force with temperature is observed in the heating phase. The variation in opening factor from 0.08 m^{1/2} to 0.04 m^{1/2} lead to the decrease in axial force by 6.11% (from 1933.92 kN to 1815.58 kN) and the residual forces got increased by 8.58 % (from 2130.282 kN to 2313.136 kN) [Figure 12].

Fire load density

In a fire model, fire load density significantly affects the maximum temperature and the time at which it is attained. clearly shows the decrease in max temperature and duration with decrease in fire load density.

Figure 12 Variation of axial forces with temperature for different opening factors

The same trend is also observed in nodal temperatures after heat transfer analysis. [Figure 10] depicts that the max temperature and time at which it is attained decreases with the decrease in fire load density.

• **Effect on Deflection**

The deflections for all the values of fire load densities follow a similar path in the heating phase and part away after reaching their respective maximum deflection. [Figure 14] For a drop of fire load density from 609 MJ/m² to 231 MJ/m², maximum deflection got decreased by 45.68%, due decrease in nodal temperatures and permanent deflections got decreased by 20.08% (from 0.0682 m to 0.0545 m).

• **Effect on axial force**

For different values of fire load densities, no significant change in the variation of axial force with temperature is observed in the heating phase. The change in fire load densities from 609 MJ/m² to 231 MJ/m², maximum axial force is increased by 0.36 % (from 2020.5 kN to 2027.9 kN) and residual force got decreased by 0.82% (from 2316.38 kN to 2297.6 kN) [Figure 13].

Thermal inertia

A compartment boundary with lower thermal inertia quickly catches fire and reaches maximum temperatures. Comparing the materials with least (432.5J/m²s^{1/2}K) and highest (1600432.5J/m²s^{1/2}K) thermal inertia [Figure 3], the maximum temperatures obtained from the fire modelling got reduced.

Figure 13 Variation of axial forces with temperature for different fire load densities

Figure 14 Variation of deflections with temperature for different fire load densities

A similar trend is observed for the nodal temperatures but, maximum nodal temperatures got reduced due to the presence of SFRM. [Figure 9] depicts that nodal temperatures are higher for the material with least thermal inertia.

Figure 15 Variation of axial force with temperature for different thermal inertia

Figure 16 variation of deflection with temperature for different thermal inertia

- **Effect on Deflection**

[Figure 16] shows that initially in the heating phase no significant deviation in deflections is observed for different values of thermal inertia, but they diverge after reaching maximum deflection. Comparing the materials of least ($432.5\text{J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$) and highest ($1600\text{J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$) thermal inertia, a decrease of 13.17% (from 0.1093 m to 0.0949 m) in the maximum deflection and a decrease of 2.13% (from 0.061 m to 0.0597 m) in the permanent deflection is observed.

- **Effect on Axial force**

For different values of thermal inertia, no significant change in the variation of axial force with temperature is observed in the heating phase. Comparing the materials of least ($432.5\text{J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$) and highest ($1600\text{J/m}^2\text{s}^{1/2}\text{K}$) thermal inertia, a decrease in 0.2% (from 2027.9 kN to 2023.7 kN) of maximum axial force and a decrease in 0.4% (from 2317.17 kN to 2307.24 kN) of residual force is observed [Figure 15].

7. CONCLUSIONS

To understand the response of a steel beam under natural fire exposure with varying fire influencing parameters, a numerical modelling study is conducted by developing a nonlinear finite element model providing insulation which reduces the nodal temperatures significantly.

The results of this study showed the percentage variation in the structural response for the corresponding percentage variation in the fire parameters. It was observed that the variation in the fire parameters do not have much influence on the structural response during heating phase but they do influence the duration at which they occur and the differences can be observed in the maximum values and in the cooling phase.

It is observed that even though the temperatures at the end of fire scenario have returned to ambient the beam experiences the residual tensile forces and permanent deflections which were not present earlier. These parameters are of major importance in the fire resistance design of steel beams. Therefore, the magnitude of these forces and deflections should be checked against the permissible values for the fire resistance design.

By comparing the results obtained, for an increase in the opening factor by 100% the change in the residual forces and permanent deflections are found to be 8.58 % and 37.84% respectively. Whereas, the same is found to be 0.82% and 20.08% for an increase in the fire load density by 163.637% and it is 0.4% and 2.13% for an increase in thermal inertia by 269.94%.

Therefore, it can be concluded that among all three parameters the thermal inertia has the least influence on the structural response of the beam under consideration even though the percentage variation in its value was much higher compared to other two factors.

REFERENCE

- [1] Negar Elhami Khorasania, , Maria Garlocka and Paolo Gardoni, “Fire load: Survey data, recent standards, and probabilistic models for office buildings,” Engineering Structures, 2014.
- [2] Alex Bwalya, “An Overview of Design Fires for Building Compartments,” 2007.
- [3] EN 1993-1-2 (2005) (English), , “Eurocode 3: Design of steel structures - Part 1-2: General rules - Structural fire Design [Authority: The European Union Per Regulation 305/2011, , Directive 98/34/EC, Directive 2004/18/EC]”.
- [4] Atif Ali Khan, Asif Usmani and Jose´ Luis Torero, “Evolution of fire models for estimating structural fire-resistance,” Fire Safety Journal , 124 (2021) 103367.
- [5] “AISC (American Institute of Steel Construction) steel construction manual 15th edition, Chicago, II, USA: AISC; 2017”.
- [6] J. P. C. R. Luís Laím, “ Numerical analysis on axially-and-rotationally restrained cold-formed,” Thin-Walled Structures, 104 (2016) 1-16.
- [7] K. N. Michal SZCZECINA*1, “Numerical Analysis of a steel frame in a Fire Situation,,” ” Inżynieria Bezpieczeństwa Obiektów Antropogenicznych, 4, (2022)..
- [8] A.Pournaghshbanda, S. Afshanb and M. Theofanousc, “Elevated temperature performance of restrained stainless steel beams,” Structures, 22 (2019) 278- 290.
- [9] A.S.Usmani, J. Rotter, S. Lamont, A. Sanad and M. Gillie, “Fundamental principles of structural behaviour under thermal effects,” Fire Safety Journal, 36 (2001) 721–744.
- [10] BS 476-20,, “Fire tests on building materials and structures –part 20: method for determination of fire resistance of elements of construction (general principles),” UK: BSI; 1987.
- [11] M. Gillie, “Analysis of heated structures: Nature and modelling benchmarks,” Fire Safety Journal, 44 (2009) 673–680.
- [12] M. Z. N. Venkatesh and K.R.Kodur, “Structural Fire Engineering”.
- [13] Naveed Iqbal, RESTRAINED BEHAVIOUR OF BEAMS IN A STEEL FRAME EXPOSED TO FIRE, Luleå, June 2013.
- [14] Qianru Guo, Kaihang Shi and Zili Jia and Ann E. Jeffe, “Probabilistic Evaluation of Structural Fire Resistance”.

- [15] S. Venkatachari and V.K.R. Kodur, “Modeling parameters for predicting the fire- induced progressive collapse in steel framed buildings,” Resilient Cities and Structures, 2 (2003) 129-144.
- [16] Vinny Gupta, G.M. Makhviladze and J.P.Roberts, “Ventilation effects on the thermal characteristics of fire spread modes in open-plan compartment fires,” Fire Safety Journal, March 2021.
- [17] Ting Xia, Hongli Ruan and Yu Wang, “Predicting the flashover occurrence and energy distribution in compartment fires with different boundary materials,” Fire Safety Journal, June 2024.
- [18] Kia-Hong Wang, Yu-Qing Liu, Pei-Hong Zhang and Yin Liang Guo, “Numerical study on the impact of wall thermal inertia on maximum smoke temperature and longitudinal attenuation in long channel fires,” International Journal of Thermal Sciences, 2023.
- [19] Ahmed El-kebir Iya , Alban Fabrice Epée , Philippe Onguéné Mvogo , Justin Tégawendé Zaida and Ruben Mouangue , “Modelling and Numerical Simulation of a Compartment Fire: Flow Rate Behaviour at Opening,” May 2023.
- [20] Andrea Lucherini, Balsa Jovanovic, Ruben Van Coile and Bart Merci, “BACKGROUND AND LIMITATIONS OF THE EUROCODE PARAMETRIC,” Applications of Structural Fire Engineering, , 11 June 2021.
- [21] T.L.Graham and etal, “The effects of the thermal inertia of the walls upon flashover development,” Fire Safety Journal, February 1999.
- [22] Yu Wang and etal, “A full-scale experimental study on single dwelling burning behavior of informal settlement,” Fire Safety Journal, March 2021.

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